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Impacts of Banditry Activities on Quality Education: An Overview of Government Schools in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina State

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Abstract

This study explores the impacts of banditry on government schools in the severely affected Jibia local government area of Katsina State. The study employed a qualitative procedure, which involved documentary analysis, revealing adverse effects on education quality, including school closures. Despite efforts from state and local governments, parents, and teachers, persistent challenges remain. The study concludes that banditry significantly impacts education quality and recommends decisive measures to enhance school security and curb banditry.

Keywords: Banditry, Impacts, Education, Jibia, Katsina State.

Introduction

In different parts of the world organized crimes have existed and are existing up till the present times. Organized crimes at present threaten all countries in both developed and developing countries (Vursavas: 2015). Organized crime refers to a group of people involved in serious criminal activities for financial gain using violence and threat of violence in most cases (DOJ: 2022). Examples of organized crime are varied which include money laundering, armed robbery, human trafficking, counterfeit currency making, drug trafficking and banditry. Banditry is a kind of organized crime committed by outlaws in remote or lawless area where there is little or no presence of government as an institution. Nigeria Crime Watch (NCW)(2011) defined banditry as an organized crime that involves the occurrence or prevalence of armed robbery or other violent crimes including the use of force or threat to that effect, to intimate a person with the intention to rob, rape or kill. It is a common genre of crime in some societies where the rule of law is almost absent as well as causing violence in contemporary societies especially in developing countries (NCW, 2011). Historical records have shown that banditry has existed in different parts of the world since the 19th century (Ladan: 2023). In Europe, bandits have operated on mountainous regions of Greece, Italy, Spain and Turkey while in Asia the bandits have also operate in mountainous regions, rocky areas and river valleys of China, India, Iran and Philippines (Ladan: 2023a). In North America, the bandits have also once existed in isolated less populated region of Mexico and USA. But in these, countries a combination of increase security presence and strict legislations against banditry including capital punishment for bandits have ended banditry.

In the continent of Africa, banditry has existed even before independence, when some of the bandits directed their aggression and violence against the colonial administration in Ethiopia/Eritrea for example (Okoli: 2021 & Rufa'i : 2021). The West African sub-region is presently bedeviled by several forms of insecurity created by armed groups one of which is the bandits. The bandits are found in several countries such as Chad, Mali, Niger Republic and Nigeria where they move freely within the porous borders. They are taking advantage of the weak security architecture in these countries and the proliferation of Small and Light Weapons (SALW) following the collapse of the late Libyan leader Colonel Mouamar Gaddafi in 2011 (Ladan & Suleiman: 2023). In Nigeria, banditry began also in 2011 as a result of the escalation of the farmers-herders conflict which has assumed a deadly and destructive dimension. It started from Zamfara State, from where it spread to all the neighboring states such as Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Niger and Sokoto. The bandits have camps in abandoned forests and forest reserves in these states from where they move on motorcycles armed with dangerous weapons to launch attacks on villages inhabited by farmers. They engage in arson, murder, robbery, cattle rustling, kidnapping for ransom and sporadic shooting to

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scare the people (Okoli: 2021). Based on these criminal activities of the bandits, it is quite obvious that banditry will affect the socio-economic activities of the inhabitants of the areas such as education at all levels. Banditry has affected primary, secondary and tertiary education in virtually all the States of the North West geo-political zone. The recent tactics adopted by the bandits to kidnap large number of pupils and students in primary and secondary schools has further worsened the situation. The first major kidnapping incident was on December 11th 2020 when a group of armed bandits kidnapped 344 students of Government Science Secondary School (GSSS) Kankara, Katsina State. Other kidnappings followed in succession in Niger, Kaduna and Zamfara States. It was following the kidnapping of some pupils from a Universal Basic Education (UBE) Primary School in Rema in Binin Gwari LGA Kaduna State on March 14th 2021 that former Vice President Atiku called on the Federal Government to declare ‘State of Emergency’ on the education sector in order to halt further incidences of kidnapping and save the educational sector from collapse (Nasiru, 2021). The kidnapping incidences and other activities of bandits led to the closure of 11,536 schools in the North West region from December 2020 to April 2022 which has impacted the education of approximately 1.3 million children in the 2020/2021 academic year (UNICEF, 2022).

Some studies have been conducted about banditry and education or the impacts of banditry on education in north western Nigeria. Sale (2021) studied the impacts of banditry on education in Faskari Local Government Area (LGA), Katsina State. The study found out that the education of school children has been severely disrupted as they were forced to leave their villages to take shelter at the local government displaced person’s camp. Smiley *et al* (2021) studied the negative impacts of violence on children’s education and wellbeing, evidence from northern Nigeria. The study found out that children who experience any kind of violence are more likely to be out of school, have reduced learning and are less likely to feel safe traveling to and from school. Rosenje *et al* (2022) examined armed banditry and the collapse of education in north western Nigeria. Findings of the study showed that armed banditry incidences hindered teaching and learning due to closure of schools, withdrawal of students from schools, decrease in school enrolment etc. Ojeleye (2022) studied insecurity as a predictor of students’ learning in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that insecurity has made students to develop a phobia to attend school as they skip lessons and school activities. The students lose interest in school activities leading to drop out, boys move into trade while girls settle down for early marriage (Ojeleye *et al.*, 2022). Sa’adu and Lawal (2023) explore the perceived effects of banditry activities on pupil’s enrolment in selected public primary schools in Gusau LGA of Zamfara State. The findings revealed that banditry activities have negative effect on children’s enrolment in public primary schools with respondents expressing concerns about the safety of their children.

From the literatures reviewed above, it can be observed that only the study by Sale (2021) focuses on one of the LGAs affected by banditry in Katsina state. This study is focusing on the impacts of banditry activities on quality education among government schools in Jibia LGA, one of the seven LGAs sharing boundary with Zamfara State (Zurmi LGA) and also one of the most affected by banditry.

Education in Jibia Local Government Area

On the state or condition of education in Jibia LGA, data presented in Table 1 indicated that education is in detrimental condition. This is because most of the schools are dilapidated, lack enough teachers, instructional materials for quality teaching and learning process. The Table also shows that the schools are in relatively good condition in terms of school buildings, and number of teachers and instructional materials. These respondents are referring to the community and private schools that are established mainly in the local government headquarter Jibia town. Furthermore, the insecurity created by banditry has led to the concentration of schools in Jibia town to the detriment of other villages whose people have migrated there or elsewhere. The tables 1, 2 and 3 below show the schools and institutions in Jibia town.

Table 1: Public Primary and Secondary Schools in Jibia town, Jibia LGA, Katsina State

S/N	Name of School	Ownership	Certificate Awarded
1	Gatari Duma Primary School, Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Primary School Leaving Certificate West African Senior Secondary School Certificate
2	Government Day Secondary School (GDSS) Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary School Certificate
3	Government Girls Unity Secondary School (GGUSS) Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Primary School Leaving Certificate Primary School Leaving Certificate
4	Muhammad Rabiu Model Primary School Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Primary School Leaving Certificate

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|---|--|
| 5 | Sule Mai Mota Primary School, Jibia, Katsina State Government
Jibia LGA |
| 6 | Tudun Tukare Primary School, Jibia, Katsina State Government
Jibia LGA |

Source: *JLGEA (2023a)*.

From Table 2 above it can be observed that Katsina State Government owns three primary and three secondary schools to provide education for pupils and students in the LGA. Since the schools are public places they, often serve as make-shift camps for persons displaced by the activities of bandits especially Muhammad Rabiu Model Primary School Jibia.

Table 2: Community Primary, Secondary Schools and Tertiary Institutions in Jibia town, Jibia LGA

S/No	Name of school/institution	Ownership	Certificate awarded
1	Hajara Community Nursery and Primary school, Jibia	Jibia Community Members	Nursery and Primary School Leaving Certificates
2	Madina Community College of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Jibia	Jibia Community Members	Senior Secondary School Leaving Certificate
3	Madina Community College of General Studies Jibia (Affiliated to Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Kaduna state)	Jibia Community Members	National Diploma Certificate
4	Women College of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Jibia	Jibia Community Members	Senior Secondary School Leaving Certificate.

Source: *JLGEA (2023a)*.

From Table 2 above, it can be observed that the members of the community in Jibia made efforts to establish four schools and an institution of higher learning to cater for the education of the people. This is in view of the obvious inadequacy of the six primary and secondary schools in the town as the population grows. However, none of the schools and the tertiary institution has been used as make-shift camp for those displaced by banditry.

Table 3: Private Nursery, Primary and Secondary Schools in Jibia town, Jibia LGA

S/No	Name of School/Institution	Ownership	Certificate Awarded
1	Citadel Group of Schools, Jibia	Private	Nursery, Primary and Secondary School Certificates
2	Citadel Group of Schools, Jibia (Diploma Section) Affiliated to ABU, Zaria	Private	Diploma in Education in various disciplines
3	Ibn Abbas Nursery and Primary School, Jibia	Private	Primary and Secondary School Leaving Certificates
4	Jibia Academy Nursery, Primary and Secondary Schools Jibia	Private	Nursery and Primary School Leaving certificates
5	Jibia International Nursery and Primary Schools, Jibia	Private	Nursery and Primary School Leaving Certificates
6	My Jeeb Academy of Science and Tahfizul Quran, Jibia	Private	Nursery, Primary and Secondary schools leaving certificates
7	Tarbiyya Nursery and Primary School, Jibia	Private	Nursery and Primary School Leaving Certificates

Source: *JLGEA (2023a)*.

From Table 3 above, it can be observed that the private sector is active in establishing schools and a tertiary institution to complement the efforts of the state government and members of the community. The establishment of some of the schools is in response to the demand for education following the relocation of some households to Jibia town due to the insecurity created by banditry in the LGA.

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Impacts of Banditry on Quality Education in Jibia Local Government Area

With regards to the impacts of banditry on quality education in Jibia LGA, data in Table 4 indicates that banditry has negatively affected education in a number of ways. The ways include creating insecurity, kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers, occupying schools to prevent schooling, forcing closure of schools, creating shortage of teachers, and school drop-outs, destroying schools, incapacitating parents, negative impacts on teacher training among others. Table 4 – 9 shows the first six ways by which the banditry affected education in Jibia LGA

Table 4: Some banditry activities that creates insecurity among government schools in Jibia LGA

S/N	Date and name of school	Banditry activities	Impacts of the banditry activities
1	May 7 th 2020 at Kange Nomadic Primary School, Jibia LGA	Bandits broke into the office of the Head Teacher to rest in the afternoon during weekend.	The Head Teacher had to run away without completing the work he went to do.
2	October 5 th 2020 at Farfaru ‘A’ Primary School, Jibia LGA	Bandits invaded part of the school as pupils were just returning from Covid-19 induced break	Closure of the school for one week as pupils became terrified seeing men with guns.
3	December 12 th 2021 at GGUSS Jibia	Bandits kidnapped 344 students from GSS Kankara Kankara LGA	Fear gripped the boarding students thinking they would be the next target of the bandits. The State government ordered the closure of all boarding schools in the State.
4	July 12 th 2021 at Gurbin Magarya Primary School, Jibia LGA	Incessant attacks on the village at night that led to the kidnapping of the mother of the Village Head.	Some parents with their children left the village for fear of being kidnapped to migrate to Jibia town.
5	September 1 st 2021 at Garin Jita Government Pilot Primary and Junior Secondary School Jibia LGA	Bandits stormed the premises of the schools holding dangerous weapons and riding their motorcycles recklessly.	Fear gripped teachers, pupils and students as Head Teacher/Principal directed the closure of the school after consulting the Local Government Education Secretary
6	May 12 th 2022 at Government Day Secondary School, Jibia	Bandits passed through the school to attack residents close to the school at night as the school had no fencing	Most of the teachers and students left the school without doing evening games/prep.
7	Mrch 20 th 2022 at Gangara Primary School, Jibia LGA	Bandits intercepted the Head Teacher along Kukar Babangida to Gangara road to snatch his motorcycle	The motorcycle snatching incident and bandit’s other nefarious activities continued leading to the closure of the school
8.	July 26 th 2022 at Government Day Secondary School Daddara, Jibia LGA	Information received at the school that bandits are approaching the school premises area	Teachers and students abandoned the National Examination Council (NECO) Biology Theory exams holding on the day.

Source: Ladan (2023b).

From table 5 above, it can be observed that there were several activities of the bandits that created insecurity which hindered teaching, learning and extra-curricular activities. The activities include breaking into offices, invading schools, reports on kidnappings, incessant attacks and passing through school premises. The impacts of the activities include inability to complete school work, closure of the schools, migration to the local government headquarters and leaving the school without doing games. These impacts in general have negative impacts on teaching and learning in the schools as they cannot take place in an insecure environment.

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Table 5: Pupils, students and teachers kidnapped at Jibia LGA

S/N	Date and location	Pupil/students or teacher kidnapped	Status/condition
1	December 19 th 2019 at Garin Gado village	A teacher of Garin Gado Primary school was kidnapped during an attack at home at night.	Released after 15 days in captivity and payment of N500, 000 ransom.
2	March 29 th 2021 outside GGUSS Jibia	A teacher of the school was kidnapped outside the school premises at night.	The teacher managed to escape but was in trauma due to the kidnapping ordeal and had to be hospitalized.
3	October 5 th 2020 at school premises Farfaru 'A' Primary school, Jibia LGA	Kidnap of two pupils of the school who were just returning from Covid-19 induced break.	Released after one week and payment of N200, 000 ransom.
4	February 5 th 2021 at Jibia township	A female student of Madina Community College of Arabic and Islamic Studies was kidnapped at gun-point on her way to the institution	The bandits called her father to demand for N20million but she was able to escape before any payment
5	March 7 th 2022 at Farfaru village	Teachers' son and pupil at Farfaru 'B' primary school kidnapped at the outskirts of the village	The pupil spent 30 days in captivity but released after the random payment of N200, 000.
6	June 4 th 2022 at Farfaru	Four pupils of Farfaru 'A' and 'B' primary schools among 80 people kidnapped during a reprisal attack on the village.	Released from captivity after one week due to the intervention of the Fulani elders of the area.

Source: Ladan (2023a).

From table 5, above it can be observed that the kidnapping incidences occurred even at the local government headquarters, Jibia. This is happening as the bandits are gaining more strength thereby becoming more daring while also employing the services of informants who live in towns and villages with the people. Two teachers were kidnapped, with one managing to escape while in the other, case ransom was paid. Eight pupils and students were kidnapped in the four instances shown on table 6. In two instances, ransom was paid which tend to impoverish the parents and even the teachers considering that the average monthly salary of a teacher in Katsina State is N70, 000. This clearly indicated that most families in the State had to sell their properties and even life savings in order to be able to pay the huge amount of money demanded as ransom by the bandits. Furthermore, the Katsina State Ministry of Education and the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) Katsina State Chapter do not assist teachers in the payment of ransom.

Table 6: Primary and secondary schools forced to close temporarily due to banditry in Jibia LGA

S/M	Name of school	Reasons for closure	Length of time closed
1	Government Girls Unity Secondary School Jibia	State government directed the closure of the school after kidnapping of GSSS Kankara	December 12 th 2020 to date.
2	Zandam Primary School Zandam Jibia LGA	Incessant attacks by the bandits made the people to flee to Magama and Jibia towns. Bandits stormed the school premises armed with dangerous weapons causing chaotic situation	January 2 nd 2021 to May 8 th 2022
3	Government Pilot Primary and Junior Secondary School Garin Jita	The whole village people fled following the withdrawal of security forces providing security	September 1 st 2021 to March 30 th 2022.
4	Shimfida Primary School, Shimfida Jibia LGA		March 10 th to August 8 th 2022 March 10 th to August 8 th 2022

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5	Government Day Secondary School Shimfida, Jibia LGA	The whole village people fled following the withdrawal of security forces providing security	May 9 th to July 18 th 2022
6	Muhammad Rabiun Model Primary School, Jibia	Displaced persons from Shimfida and Farfaru villages occupied classes as temporary shelter	June 4 th to July 3 rd 2022
7	Farfaru 'A' and 'B' Primary Schools, Farfaru	Large scale attacks on the village involving killings, kidnappings, looting and burning of houses	October 5 th 2020 to date (2023)
8	Government Day Secondary School Gangara, Jibia :GA	Incessant attacks on the village by the bandits made the people to flee to other villages	

Source: JLGEA (2023b), Ladan (2023a)

From table 6 above, it can be observed that various reasons are responsible for the closure of the schools. In the first instance, it was a directive by the State Government following the GSS Kankara incidence. The students of the schools were relocated to Government Girls College Katsina when the school resumed. Other directives to close the schools were made by the Education Secretary of the local government in order to ensure the safety and security of the pupils, students and teachers. The length of time of the closure differs depending on the reason for the closure. Only in one instance did the occupation of the school by displaced persons led to the closure of the school with the pupils divided among other primary schools in Jibia town. It is important to observe here that while the school listed on table 7 remain closed though temporarily, other schools in the State remained open with their pupils and students engaging in learning. In instances where the pupils were moved to another school, the receiving school became overpopulated and congested making teaching and learning difficult.

Table 7: Schools presently occupied by bandits, displaced persons and security forces in Jibia LGA

S/No.	Name of school	Those occupying the school	Reasons for the occupation of the school
1	Fafara Primary School Fafara	Bandits occupied the school sleeping during the day time and relaxing in the classrooms	Bandits have taken over the village due to lack of security forces to guard the village like nearby Shimfida.
2	Government Girls Unity Secondary School Jibia	Displaced persons from Zangon Farfaru and Kwari villages	No any vacant public building in Jibia town to serve as displaced person's camp
3	Government day Secondary School Gangara	Bandits using the school building to rest and relax	Most of the inhabitant of the village have fled and nobody at the school
4	School Shimfida	About 2,000 soldiers occupy the school as their base to secure the villages against banditry	No any vacant public building that can accommodate the number of the soldiers in the village.
5	Tsamben Radi Primary School, Tsamben Radi	Bandits have occupied the school using it as a transit point while coming out of their forest hideout.	Most of the people of the village have fled due to incessant attacks with nobody to enforce law or order.
6	Tagwaye Primary School, Tagwaye	Bandits occupied the school as a transit point in and out of their forest hideout.	The whole village has been displaced with the inhabitants fleeing to Gurbin Baure or neighboring villages in Niger Republic.

Source : Abdullahi (2023) and Ladan (2023b).

From table 7 above, it can be observed that all the six schools were occupied by bandits, displaced persons or security forces. In the case of Fafara Primary school, (serial number 1) some of the ex-students of the school who attended secondary school at Shimfida have become bandits themselves according to one of the teachers. In serial numbers 2 and 4, it was because of lack of any vacant public building to accommodate the troops and displaced persons that led to the occupation of the schools. For serial number 3, 5 and 6 the villages have been taken over or most of the people have fled which led to the occupation. In all the six cases there are no any teaching and learning activities going on in the schools which is detrimental to their educational development.

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Table 8 : Primary and secondary schools closed from October 2020 to date in Jibia LGA

S/no	Name of school	Ward school is located	Reason for closure
1	Falale Primary School, Falale	Bugaje ward	Incessant attacks on the village as it is close to a cattle route leading to forest den of the bandits
2	Gangara Primary School Gangara	Gangara ward	Attacks on the people including blocking of the road coming into the village
	Tankuri Primary School, Tankuri	Gangara ward	Increasing frequency of attacks on the village has made it insecure forcing most of the people to flee.
3	Yangayya Primary School Yangayya	Yangayya ward	Attacks on the people have created insecurity leading to migration out of the village
	Matso-Matso Primary School	Mazanya ward	Attacks on the people, robberies and kidnapping has made the whole village insecure.
4	Matso-Matso	Yangayya ward	Sporadic attacks on the village as some bandits have camped in nearby Zandam forest
5	Mazanya Primary School, Mazanya	Yangayya ward	Bandits have made the school insecure as they pass around the school armed with guns
	Farfaru "A" Primary School, Farfaru	Mazanya ward	Incessant kidnapping incidences as village lies along road intersected by cattle route
6	Karauki Primary School, Karauki	Mazanya ward	Incessant kidnapping incidences as the village lies along a road intersected by cattle route
7	Tsayau Primary School. Tsayau	Farfaru ward	The Fulani people and their children who inhabit the village have fled due to cattle rustling
	Kyabbo Nomadic Primary School	Faru-Maje ward	
8	Kyabbo	Mallamawa ward	
9		Mallamawa ward	

Source : JLGEA (2023b)

From table 8 above, it can be observed that ten schools from seven wards were closed after the Covid-19 induced break in October 2020 to date (September 2023). The schools were closed due to the insecurity arising from banditry either on the village where the schools are located or on the schools themselves. According to the JLGEA (2023b) the total number of pupils from the schools is 8,576 comprising 3,674 males and 4, 576 females. Thirty percent (30%) of the pupils of the schools have been relocated to other more secure school while seventy percent (70%) could not be relocated due to the distance involved from the villages and even most of the inhabitants have been forced to flee (Abdullahi, 2023). Banditry has negatively affected education by creating shortage of teachers. This occurred as many teachers refuse posting to schools where villages are affected by banditry. Even in situations where they accepted and start to report for duty, they then seek for re-posting out of the schools. For example, Gurbin Magarya primary school, Gurbin Magarya with a population of 938 pupils has only six teachers but at one time only one teacher was attending the school due to banditry. This occurred as the other five teachers sought for transfer out of the village.

Banditry has led to school dropouts as many pupils and students in the LGA were forced to stop going to school. Many students whose schools were forced to close due to the activities of the bandits hardly join or enroll into another school. Also most pupils and students whose parents migrated to Jibia town to stay at make-shift camps drop out as they have limited access to learning facilities. This happened as there is no existing government policy for immediate transfer of pupils/students to another school as a result of the displacement. Furthermore, most students who became orphans due to banditry drop out of school as they had nobody to support them to go back to school (Ladan and Liman, 2021).

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Banditry has negatively affected education by incapacitating parents who find it difficult to engage in farming and cattle rearing. The results are that they have no money to enroll or register their children into schools, buy school uniforms and books and pay for examination fees when the need arises. The payment of ransom to the bandits to secure the release of loved ones further impoverish them especially as there is no any form of assistance from the State or local government council. Banditry has negatively affected teacher training in Jibia LGA and others LGAs affected by the activities of bandits. For example, in May/June 2022 teachers attending the Teacher Development Training Programme for 32,000 Katsina State Public School Teachers requested the Facilitator to summaries the training module. This was to allow them to go back to their respective destinations before it got dark, which was the time bandits come out of their hide outs to launch attacks. This was the same during the training of teachers from Kankara LGA at Malumfashi when the training program closed by 3.00pm instead of 5.00pm.

Banditry has made some teachers to incur food and economic loss. This occurred as some enterprising teachers posted to villages engaged in farming activities which allowed them to cultivate and harvest food crops. For example, a teacher based at Jibia town but posted to Shimfida village hired a farmland to cultivate 100 bundles of guinea corn and 50 bundles of millet every farming season in 6-years. Another teacher posted to Government Day Secondary School Gangara cultivated and harvested beans within the school premises including guinea corn and sesame seeds. Both the teachers have presently been deployed to Katsina and Jibia where such lands are not available. Banditry has led to the destruction of schools in the form of setting the school buildings and facilities on fire. For example, following the withdrawal of security forces and the people from Shimfida village on March 18th 2022 the bandits set the primary and secondary schools on fire. Besides destruction through burning, the bandits have been engaged in removing the roofing sheets and wood loggings of primary, secondary and community junior secondary schools at Gangara and Tankuri villages from March 29th – 31st 2023. The destructions make the schools inhabitable for any teaching and learning process and will require rehabilitation in a situation when banditry ceases and security returns.

Response of Katsina State Government on Banditry Activities

Katsina State Government has responded in a number of ways to the negative impacts of banditry on education in Jibia LGA and the state in general.

1. Following the kidnapping of 344 students of GSSS Kankara on December 11th the State government on December 12th 2020 directed the closure of all boarding secondary schools in the state. In line with this directive GGUSS Jibia, a girl's secondary school was closed and the students directed to go home.
2. The Education Secretary of Jibia LGA after receiving complains about the insecurity arising from banditry also directed for the closure of schools on temporary basis. Some of the schools were reopened when the security situation improved in the affected villages.
3. The Education Secretary also carried out inspection visits to some schools in Jibia and Magama where he urged teachers deployed to the most affected villages to report to his office for reposting in order to guarantee their safety and security.
4. The Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) has provided a make-shift structure close to Muhammad Rabiou Model Primary School Jibia that served as a school for the children of the persons displaced from March 10th to August 8th 2022. However, the parents who stayed at GGUSS Jibia lamented that their children numbering over 3,000 were not taught as well during the same period (Ibrahim, 2022).
5. From June 2022 – May 2023 the State Government sponsored a radio announcement aired by Katsina State Radio Service with the voice of former Governor Masari urging parents, pupils and students to return to school. The announcement also urged parents that bandits should not be allowed to destroy the education of the children of the State.
6. Katsina State government under Governor Masari was reported to have spent the sum of N88.6m in order to rehabilitate the two schools burnt by the bandits including the burnt houses of the people of Shimfida (Taoheed, 2022). This is important as it enabled the pupils and students of the two schools to resume schooling after the displacement incident.
7. The State Ministry of Education directed all schools to form security committees and appoint a security master to take charge of security issues in both primary and secondary schools throughout the State. In boarding schools, improvements were made in wall fencing and there was the provision of mobile policemen at the entrance gate to monitor movements in and out of the schools.

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Response of Parents and Teachers on Banditry Activities

Parents and teachers as stakeholders in the educational sector have express concern about the impacts of banditry on education in the LGA. They have responded in a number of ways which are outlined below:

1. Some parents have migrated out of Jibia LGA to relocate to Katsina, the state capital or to Maradi, the capital of Maradi region in Niger Republic just 50kms away from Jibia town. This occurred as even Jibia town was attacked by the bandits five times from 2019 – 2023.
2. Most of the parents have withdrawn their daughters from GGUSS Jibia due to fear of kidnapping and enrolled them into other schools which are mostly day secondary schools. This is the situation with most of the parents in the State following the GSS Kankara kidnapping incident in December 2020.
3. Most of the teachers posted to the most affected areas demand for transfer to another school to avoid an encounter with the bandits. Those teachers who could not get transferred avoid regular attendance and as such select some days to go to school while staying at home on some days.
4. Teachers do not wear new clothes to schools and as such wear old ones thereby avoid looking rich or wealthy which will attract the attention of the bandits to plan kidnapping or robbery.
5. Teachers who ride motorcycles to go to school make the motorcycles to look old to avoid snatching by the bandits. Also, the teachers do not maintain one route while going to school and as such use to change routes to avoid monitoring and targeting for kidnappings by the bandits.
6. Some of the teachers have joined the local vigilante groups that engages in regular patrol of the residential areas particularly at night to prevent attacks by the bandits. In situations where the attacks are occurring, they try to foil such attacks by counter attacking the bandits using locally made weapons.
7. Some of the teachers of the LGA have organized themselves into a coalition of Civil Society Organization (CSO). The CSO was able to collect statistics about primary and secondary education in the LGA which was presented to the candidates of the political parties contesting for membership of the Federal House of Representatives and the Senate for intervention to save education in Jibia LGA in March 2023.

Conclusion

Banditry activities has negatively impacted the quality of education throughout north western Nigeria from 2011 to date (2023). Katsina State is the first State in the North West zone that witnessed the kidnapping of a large number of students from their school. Jibia LGA is one of the areas most affected by banditry activities as it shares boundary with Zurmi LGA of Zamfara State and in close proximity to Dumburum forest, one of the major hubs of the bandits. This besides, other forest areas within the LGA such as Shabba and Tsayau forests that also served as hideouts to the bandits. The results is that banditry has negatively impacted the quality of education by creating insecurity in schools, kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers, occupying schools, creating shortage of teachers and school drop-outs, incapacitating parents to send their children to schools, closure of schools, affecting teacher training, food and economic loss to the teachers and destruction of schools. The State and local governments have responded in a number of ways with a view to reducing the negative impacts. But the responses have not been adequate and effective in substantially reducing the impacts on quality of education in the LGA. It is based on this those parents and teachers on their own adopted measures aimed also at responding to the insecurity arising from the banditry activities. It is therefore time for the federal and State governments to adopt new measures and strategies to end banditry in the North West geopolitical zone to save the education of the present generation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered towards reducing the negative impacts of banditry on education in Jibia LGA and Katsina State:

1. School safety and security should be taught at all levels of education from primary to secondary school to serve as guidance to pupils and students on what to do in case of any security breach by bandits or other criminals.
2. The International Day to Prevent Education from Attacks September 9th should be well celebrated particularly in primary and secondary schools. This can be done through lectures, drama and symposia to create awareness about safety and security in schools including tertiary institutions.
3. The Local Government Education Authority of Jibia should try to recruit teachers who are natives of the villages where the schools are located. This strategy will allow teaching to go on as it is observed that bandits usually target teachers who come from other places for kidnapping or robbery.

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4. Primary and secondary schools destroyed by bandits should be rehabilitated especially the recent ones whose roofings and wood loggings were removed. Also part of the renovations should include perimeter wall fencing to prevent trespassing by unauthorized persons such as the bandits.
5. The State Government through the State House of Assembly should formulate policies to ensure that there is immediate transfer of pupils and students displaced to other school where they have relocated. Displaced persons camps should be built in some local government headquarters to provide accommodation to those displaced instead of using primary and secondary schools.
6. Teachers deployed to the most affected villages should be trained adequately on security with a view to equipping them with more strategies of responding to the threats posed by the bandits to them and the school environment.
7. Katsina State Government in conjunction with Jibia Local Government Council should provide hazard allowances to teachers posted to schools whose villages are frequently attacked by bandits. This will provide some form of encouragement for the teachers to be attending to their lessons and reporting to duty regularly.
8. The President and Commander in-chief of the Nigerian Armed Forces should as a matter of urgency declare state of emergency on the security situation in the North West. After which a massive air and ground offensive should be launched on the forest hideouts of the bandits to decimate them once and for all.

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